

Supplementary Figure 1. Distribution of gene-level methylation differences across tissues and ant castes, shown as weighted gene methylation scores. Histograms illustrate the distribution of score values for the brain versus fat body comparison (purple), uninfected queens versus uninfected workers in the fat body (blue), and in the brain (orange). The weighted scores reflect the direction and consistency of CpG-level methylation changes within each gene, combining the mean signed methylation difference of all DMS with the \log_2 number of DMS (see Methods).

Supplementary Figure 2. Density distribution of gene-level methylation differences across tissues and ant castes, shown as weighted gene methylation scores. Density plots illustrate the distribution of score values for the brain versus fat body comparison (purple), uninfected queens versus uninfected workers in the fat body (blue), and in the brain (orange). The weighted scores reflect the direction and consistency of CpG-level methylation changes within

each gene, combining the mean signed methylation difference of all DMS with the \log_2 number of DMS (see Methods).